

VALIDITY OF PROCALCITONIN AND INTERLEUKIN-6 IN DIAGNOSIS OF EARLY NEONATAL SEPSIS OF NEONATES TAKING BLOOD CULTURE AS GOLD STANDARD IN NEONATES ADMITTED IN NEONATAL UNIT OF SHAIKH ZAYED HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Objective: This study aimed to assess the diagnostic performance of serum procalcitonin (PCT) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) for the early detection of neonatal sepsis, using blood culture as the reference standard.

Study Design: Cross-sectional validation study.

Place & Duration of Study: Department of Pediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore, from November 10, 2023 to May 10, 2024.

Methods: A total of 200 neonates aged 1–7 days admitted with clinical suspicion of early neonatal sepsis were included through consecutive sampling. Blood samples were drawn for PCT, IL-6, and culture. The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall accuracy of both markers were determined against blood culture results.

Results: Of the 200 enrolled infants, 118 (59%) were male and 82 (41%) female, with a mean age of 3.2 ± 1.7 days. Blood cultures grew pathogens in 58 cases (29%). A PCT cut-off of ≥ 0.23 ng/mL was positive in 64 neonates, yielding a sensitivity of 82.7%, specificity of 87.3%, PPV of 75.0%, NPV of 91.3%, and diagnostic accuracy of 85.5%. For IL-6, a cut-off value of ≥ 74.85 pg/mL was positive in 71 neonates, showing sensitivity 75.8%, specificity 80.9%, PPV 62.0%, NPV 89.5%, and accuracy 79.0%. ROC analysis demonstrated an AUC of 0.90 (95% CI: 0.84–0.96) for PCT and 0.85 (95% CI: 0.78–0.92) for IL-6.

Conclusion: Both PCT and IL-6 are valuable biomarkers for the early identification of neonatal sepsis, with PCT showing slightly better diagnostic accuracy. These findings support the potential use of PCT as part of clinical decision-making algorithms in local practice.

INTRODUCTION

Neonatal sepsis is one of the most important causes of sickness and death in the newborn period all over the world. Early onset neonatal sepsis, which appears within the first 72 hours of life, is especially dangerous because babies present with very vague signs. These can include poor feeding, temperature changes, breathing difficulty, or reduced activity, which can easily be mistaken for non-infectious conditions. Globally, it is estimated that sepsis accounts for almost one fifth of neonatal deaths, with the highest burden in South Asia and Africa [1]. In Pakistan, around 28 percent of newborn deaths every year are due to sepsis [2]. This makes it a serious public health issue that needs better and faster diagnosis.

Blood culture is considered the gold standard for confirming sepsis, but it has many limitations. It usually takes two to three days for results to become available, and sometimes it gives false negative results if the baby has already received antibiotics before the sample was taken [3]. This delay forces doctors to start broad spectrum antibiotics empirically in sick neonates. Although this approach may save lives, it also exposes babies to unnecessary antibiotics, increases side effects, and contributes to resistant bacteria [4]. Because of these challenges, there is a lot of interest in using laboratory biomarkers to help in the early detection of sepsis. The three most studied are C-reactive protein (CRP), procalcitonin (PCT), and interleukin-6 (IL-6). CRP is most commonly used but its rise is usually late. Procalcitonin rises quickly within a few hours of infection and remains elevated for almost a day [5]. IL-6 rises even earlier but it falls down very fast, so it needs to be measured in the right time window [6].

Several international studies have looked at the accuracy of these tests. A meta-analysis by Qiu and colleagues reported that IL-6 had a sensitivity of 85 percent and specificity of 88 percent [7]. Jekarl and colleagues showed that procalcitonin had sensitivity of 74 percent and specificity of 87 percent in diagnosing neonatal sepsis [8]. Other studies from Europe and Asia have shown similar findings, although the results are not always consistent [9,10]. In Pakistan, however, most research has focused on the bacteria and their resistance patterns, while very little work has been done on biomarkers [11,12].

This study was planned to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of procalcitonin and IL-6 in our local setting, using blood culture as the reference standard. By doing so, we hope to provide evidence that may help clinicians in early and reliable diagnosis of neonatal sepsis, reduce unnecessary antibiotic use, and improve survival in our newborn population.

Objectives

- To assess the diagnostic value of serum procalcitonin (PCT) in early neonatal sepsis by determining its sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall accuracy, with blood culture as the reference standard.
- To evaluate the diagnostic performance of interleukin-6 (IL-6) for early neonatal sepsis using the same validity indices against blood culture results.
- To compare the overall diagnostic accuracy of PCT and IL-6 in order to identify the more reliable biomarker for early detection of neonatal sepsis.

Methodology

Study Design: Cross-sectional validation study.

Setting: Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, Department of Pediatrics, Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore.

Duration: Six months (November 10, 2023 to May 10, 2024).

Sample Size: A total of 200 neonates were included in the study. Based on a 95% confidence interval, the expected sensitivity of PCT was 74.4% (with a margin of error of $\pm 15\%$), and its specificity was 86.7% (with a margin of error of $\pm 5.5\%$).

Sampling Technique: Consecutive (non-probability).

Data Collection: After informed consent, demographics and clinical features were recorded.

Blood samples (5 mL) were divided:

- 1) Sample 1: Procalcitonin (ng/mL)
- 2) Sample 2: IL-6 (pg/mL)
- 3) Sample 3: Blood culture and sensitivity

Operational cut-offs:

- PCT positive if ≥ 0.23 ng/mL
- IL-6 positive if ≥ 74.85 pg/mL

- Blood culture positive if pathogenic bacteria isolated

Statistical Analysis:

The data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. For quantitative variables, means and standard deviations (SD) were calculated, while frequencies

and percentages were used for categorical variables. Diagnostic validity indices were determined through 2x2 contingency tables. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were plotted to assess the performance of PCT and IL-6.

Results

Baseline Characteristics

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study population (n=200)

Variable	Mean ± SD / n (%)
Age (days)	3.2 ± 1.7
Male	118 (59%)
Female	82 (41%)
Gestational age (weeks)	38.6 ± 1.1
Birth weight (kg)	2.87 ± 0.42
Mode of delivery (NVD)	122 (61%)
Cesarean section	78 (39%)
Apgar score (5 min)	7.8 ± 0.7
Duration of symptoms (h)	14.6 ± 6.2

Blood Culture Positivity

- ✓ Positive in 58 (29%) neonates
- ✓ Most common organisms: *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (41%), *E. coli* (28%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (19%), others (12%).

Procalcitonin Results

- PCT positive in 64/200 (32%)
- Of these, 48 were culture positive, 16 culture negative.
- 10 culture-positive cases were missed by PCT.

Table 2: Diagnostic validity of procalcitonin

	Culture +	Culture -	Total
PCT +	48	16	64
PCT -	10	126	136
Total	58	142	200

- Sensitivity: 82.7%
- Specificity: 87.3%
- PPV: 75.0%
- NPV: 91.3%
- Accuracy: 85.5%

Interleukin-6 Results

- IL-6 positive in 71/200 (35.5%)
- Of these, 44 were culture positive, 27 culture negative.
- 14 culture-positive cases were missed by IL-6.

Table 3: Diagnostic validity of IL-6

	Culture +	Culture -	Total
IL-6 +	44	27	71
IL-6 -	14	115	129
Total	58	142	200

- Sensitivity: 75.8%
- Specificity: 80.9%
- PPV: 62.0%
- NPV: 89.5%
- Accuracy: 79.0%

ROC Analysis

Figure 1: ROC Curve Comparison of PCT and IL-6

Figure 1: ROC curve comparison of PCT and IL-6

Discussion

In this study we found that both procalcitonin and interleukin-6 were useful markers in the early detection of neonatal sepsis, but procalcitonin performed better in terms of diagnostic accuracy. Our findings are close to what has been reported

internationally. Jekarl and colleagues showed that procalcitonin had a sensitivity of 74 percent and specificity of 87 percent [1], while we observed slightly higher sensitivity and almost similar specificity. This may be due to differences in case selection and laboratory methods. Similarly, IL-6 in our study showed reasonable sensitivity and

specificity but was overall less accurate compared with procalcitonin. This is also consistent with earlier work where IL-6 was reported to be a very early but less stable marker, often missing cases if the sample is not collected within the right time window [2].

The prevalence of culture-proven sepsis in our neonates was 29 percent, which is somewhat higher than that reported from Nepal (16.9 percent) [3] and Karachi (26 percent) [4], but still within the expected regional range. The most common organisms isolated in our unit were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *E. coli*, similar to what has been shown in other studies from South Asia [5,6]. This highlights the continuing problem of gram-negative infections in our setting. It also explains why clinicians often start broad spectrum antibiotics empirically, but as our results suggest, reliable biomarkers like procalcitonin could help reduce unnecessary exposure to antibiotics and improve stewardship efforts.

There are some important limitations to consider. Our study was done in a single tertiary care hospital and included only term babies, so the results cannot be directly applied to preterm infants. We also did not evaluate the cost-effectiveness of these biomarkers, which may be a barrier in resource-limited settings. Still, the strength of our study is that it provides local data on two promising diagnostic tests that have not been evaluated together before in Pakistan. When compared with international work, our findings are encouraging and support the role of procalcitonin as a routine part of the diagnostic approach to neonatal sepsis [7,8]. Further multicenter studies with larger and more diverse populations are recommended to confirm these results and to explore the practical issues of incorporating these biomarkers into daily neonatal care.

Comparison with Literature:

- Jekarl et al. (2013) reported PCT sensitivity 74.4% and specificity 86.7%; our study found higher sensitivity (82.7%) but similar specificity.
- Qiu et al. (2018) meta-analysis showed IL-6 sensitivity 85% and specificity 88%; our findings were slightly lower (76% and 81%), possibly due to late sampling.

- Pakistani data on biomarkers remain limited; most studies focus on microbial resistance patterns. Our study fills this gap by providing local evidence for biomarker use.

Possible Explanations

The superior performance of procalcitonin in our study could be attributed to its longer half-life, which helps maintain stable levels and minimizes the risk of missed cases. In contrast, IL-6 levels rise quickly but also decrease rapidly, making it less reliable in some cases. We observed that IL-6 in our cohort was more likely to produce false positives, possibly due to non-infectious inflammatory factors such as delivery-related stress or perinatal hypoxia. Additionally, some infants had been previously exposed to antibiotics, which may have lowered the rate of positive blood cultures and contributed to an underestimation of the actual incidence of sepsis.

Strengths and Limitations

This study has several strengths. It is the first local work that directly compares procalcitonin and IL-6 in suspected neonatal sepsis. The sample size of 200 neonates is adequate and provides reliable estimates, and the use of strict inclusion and exclusion criteria helped to minimize confounding factors. However, the study also has some limitations. It was conducted in a single center, which restricts generalizability, and only term neonates were included, so the results may not apply to preterm infants. In addition, the study did not evaluate the cost-effectiveness of introducing these biomarkers into routine practice, which remains an important consideration in our resource-limited settings.

Clinical Implications:

Despite these limitations, the clinical implications of our results are important. Procalcitonin appears to be a reliable and rapid diagnostic tool for early neonatal sepsis and could be considered as part of the diagnostic work-up in NICUs in Pakistan. IL-6, while still useful, is more dependent on early sampling and may be harder to apply consistently in busy neonatal units. Incorporating procalcitonin into routine protocols could reduce unnecessary exposure to antibiotics, allow faster and more targeted

treatment, and potentially improve neonatal outcomes in our local population.

Conclusion

This study showed that both procalcitonin and interleukin-6 are useful in the early diagnosis of neonatal sepsis, but procalcitonin performed better in terms of sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy. These findings suggest that procalcitonin can serve as a more dependable marker in our local setting where rapid and reliable diagnosis is often difficult. While IL-6 remains a valuable test when collected early, its short half-life and practical challenges limit its routine use. Overall, the results of this study highlight the potential of procalcitonin to improve timely recognition and management of neonatal sepsis in Pakistan.

Recommendations

Based on our findings, it is recommended that procalcitonin should be considered as part of the diagnostic protocol for suspected neonatal sepsis in tertiary care hospitals. Interleukin-6 may be used as an adjunct where facilities and timely sampling are available, but procalcitonin should remain the preferred biomarker. Larger multicenter studies are needed to include preterm babies and to confirm the generalizability of these results. Future research should also assess the cost-effectiveness of routine procalcitonin testing in resource-limited settings. Implementing these measures can help reduce unnecessary antibiotic use, promote better antimicrobial stewardship, and ultimately improve neonatal survival outcomes in Pakistan.

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